

Cultural, Linguistic, and Literary Identity Through Drama and Theatre as a Continuation of Cognitive and Evaluative Processes Concerning the Arbëresh Contribution

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The historical migration of the Arbëresh community during the two-century period of the fifteenth and sixteenth centuries was accompanied by persistent efforts to preserve tradition from an anthropological perspective, including customs and, above all, language. Language functioned not only as an identifying element, but also as a unifying, communicative, and conserving force, from the earliest settlements to the present day.

Cultural identity is a matter of “being.” It belongs to the future as much as to the past [...] Cultural identities come from somewhere, they have histories, but like everything that is historical, they undergo constant transformation; they are subject to the continuous “play” of history, culture, and power (Hall, Stuart & Paul Du Gay 2012).

Beginning in the eighteenth century, Arbëresh intellectuals (Mandalà 2018) scientifically documented and demonstrated the historical position of the Arbëresh people. This marked an extremely important step for the community, because self-recognition and the resolution of the “question of origin” permanently connected them with Albanian history and culture.

In his study *Primitive Culture* (Tylor 2016), culture is defined as a complex whole that includes knowledge, beliefs, arts, morals, laws, and all other abilities or habits acquired by humans as members of society. This anthropological definition is complemented by the sociological perspective, according to which culture is a generalizing term referring to the symbolic dimension of human society—a conscious creation of human rationality that implies a collection of ideas and symbols manifested within social structure (Marshall 1998).

Cultural studies have treated culture as language, representation, instrument, practice, and artifact. Contemporary theory also views culture as a syncretic product of relationships and connections between the local and the global (Barker 2004). In this context, the term cultural identity refers to the identification of a social group—specifically the Arbëresh of Italy—with a maternal ethnocultural and linguistic tradition, namely Albanian culture, tradition, and language.

The primary identifying and conserving element, as mentioned above, remains the preservation of language as the central component of Arbëresh life (G. S. Di Maggio 2020). Cultivated through literature and alongside other social and cultural components, language “recreated” the homeland on foreign soil through intellectual, literary, cultural, and journalistic activity (Shkurtaj 2007).

This idea is further strengthened through the cultivation of drama as a genre, which provided the opportunity to allegorically reflect existential conditions and linguistic preservation (Calivà 2021).

The issue of the “myth of Albanian origin” was first addressed in the cultural magazines *Omnibus* (1833), founded by Vincenzo Torelli, and *L’Oreteo* (1839), founded by Francesco Crispi (Mandalà 2018).

Later, the tradition of writing about Arbëresh and Albanian history, culture, and literature continued in journals such as *Shqiptari i Italisë* (1848), *Fiamuri i Arbërit* (1883), *Arbri i Ri*, *Ylli i Arbëreshëve*, *Lajmëtari i Shqipërisë*, *La Nazione Albanese* (1886), *Zgjimi* (1963), *Zjarri* (1970), *Katundi Ynë* (1970), *Basilicata Comunità Arbëreshe*, *Zëri i Arbëreshvet* (1972), *Jeta Arbëreshe*, *Lajmëtari i Arbëreshëve* (1972), *Mondo Albanese* (1975), *Vatra Jonë* (1956–1973), *Lidhja* (1980), *Rilindja Arbëreshe* (1981), *Gjuha Jonë*, *Kamastra*, *Vija* (1976), *Pranvera* (1987), and others.

It was precisely the newspaper *Fiamuri i Arbërit*, founded by Jeronim de Rada, that in 1887 published the drama *Emira* by F. A. Santori. This corpus of Arbëresh newspapers and magazines represents a multidimensional archive—historical, linguistic, cultural, literary, social, and political—which serves not only researchers and critics, but especially younger generations and collective memory.

The risk of losing cultural and linguistic identity has encouraged the Arbëresh community to create numerous spaces for literary, cultural, and media activities in order to ensure continuous language practice. Thus, in several major Arbëresh centers, radio stations were established in the late twentieth century, broadcasting exclusively in Arbëresh, such as *Radio Skanderbeg* in San Demetrio, *Radio Libero* in Castrovillari, and others in Ungra and Hora.

Today, two central goals of Arbëresh literature and journalism are the preservation of religious rites and the Albanian language, as well as strengthening cultural contacts between Arbëresh communities in Italy and Albanians in the Balkans and the wider diaspora (Shkurtaj 2007). Issues such as migration outside Arbëresh villages, interethnic marriage, language preservation, and protection of ethnic identity remain central themes in contemporary Arbëresh literature, drama, and theatre.

Leading figures in European education have formulated theories and arguments regarding theatre within academic institutions. Theatre requires space, while universities seek new methods to renew teaching practices and enhance effectiveness (Corsi 2003).

In this context, theatre functions as a powerful formative element and as a dramatic laboratory experience, allowing students to engage with texts traditionally accessed only through reading. Specifically, we refer to Anton Santori’s drama *Emira*, considered the first structurally formed Albanian drama and a unique contribution to national dramaturgy.

Emira is recognized as the first original drama written in Albanian. It was published irregularly: the first three acts appeared in De Rada’s *Fiamuri i Arbërit* in November 1887, while the remaining acts were published in De Rada’s 1896 anthology. An attempt at republication was made by Ziaudin Kodra in 1959, and the complete five-act version was republished in 1984 by Francesco Solano (Sauku–Bruci 2013).

Equally important is the biographical understanding of Santori as Albania's first dramatist. As Elsie (1997) notes, the Romantic cultural awakening of the Arbëresh in the mid-nineteenth century produced another original literary talent. Francesco Antonio Santori (1819–1894) was born in Santa Caterina Albanese. After abandoning monastic life, he worked as a teacher and craftsman and later served as a parish priest until his death.

Since the term “drama” encompasses all theatrical forms from text to performance, and since *Emira* fulfills the essential elements of classical drama—conflict development, psychological tension, and structural composition—it was selected for staging.

Through aesthetic and artistic exploration (Bakhtin 1981), critical analysis, and practical performance, students experienced theatrical principles directly. Character construction was achieved through semiotic textual and scenic systems, analyzed during pre-stage rehearsals as experimental simulations of conflict situations (Czertok 1999).

Students gained insight into the relationship between Albanian drama history and theatre, social movements, philosophical and aesthetic concepts, anthropological elements, ethnography, costume design, and lifestyle representation.

The dramatic space was structured through actantial projections of the narrative world, following Lotman (1994) and Ibersfeld (2006). Acting performances by characters such as Kalina, Emira, Kallonjeri, and Moriani emphasized philosophical and ethical values including virtue, faith, modest living, and spiritual love.

Scenic construction relied on authorial stage directions and indirect textual cues, transformed into expressive scenography. Both traditional textual interpretation (Pavis 2003) and modern meta-directorial approaches were applied.

The classical dramatic structure, with choral elements inspired by ancient tragedy, enabled minimalist scenography and symbolic staging. A Brechtian “choral voice” expanded narrative space and dramatic impact.

Modern theatrical adaptation required role synthesis. Seven bandit characters were performed by a single actor using gesture and expressive differentiation, creating a powerful innovative effect. As Freud (2005) states, theatre depends on identification and catharsis, producing emotional release.

Emira successfully met the challenges of modern theatrical adaptation.

Modern reading theory raises semantic questions about how meaning is expressed and what the dramatic text signifies (Szondi 2000). Dramatic composition, structure, and reception theory proved essential to interpretation.

Performing in Arbëresh posed linguistic challenges, but through rehearsals, transcription consultation, and dramatic immersion, the performance achieved authenticity and emotional resonance.

Special emphasis was placed on emotional engagement, diction, pronunciation, logical and rhythmic stress, and intonation techniques.

Staging *Emira* promoted a new learning method based on dramatic action and interpersonal theatrical communication. As Bologna (2007) notes, performance creates identity by transforming narrative presence into lived experience.

Students are often treated as abstract entities, while effective educational proxemics (Alter 1981) are frequently absent. Theatre provided an interactive communicative environment for intellectual and cultural exchange.

On stage, *Emira* functioned as an interactive system of verbal, non-verbal, gestural, musical, and visual languages (Beneventi 2006). It became a multidisciplinary educational tool and symbolic-semiotic learning mechanism.

Classical Arbëresh tradition thus emerged as a cultural, literary, pedagogical, and didactic experience that stimulated continued learning, reading, and critical engagement with Arbëresh contributions in both academic and theatrical spaces.

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